

Guide for the Design of TPMS Catalytic Supports by FFF: Part 1 Recommendations for the process

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1. Design and Geometric Modeling

For complex internal architectures, such as TPMS or lattice structures, the use of implicit modeling tools (e.g., nTopology) is highly recommended over traditional parametric (CAD-based) approaches.

- Implicit modeling defines geometry mathematically through scalar fields, which enables more efficient and stable boolean operations. This approach maintains geometric fidelity and drastically reduces processing time, regardless of the geometric complexity and without the need for prior simplification.

2. Processing and 3D Printing

TPMS can be manufactured without the need for support structures when they are properly oriented along the Z-axis, as their continuous geometry promotes stable deposition. For strut-based lattice structures, support structures are also not required, provided that the overhang angle exceeds 30°.

2.1. General Hardware Recommendations

- **Nozzle:** The use of a 0.6 mm hardened steel nozzle is mandatory due to the highly abrasive nature of copper and alumina-filled filaments, preventing excessive wear and ensuring dimensional consistency.
- **Build Plate:** A PEI build plate is recommended because it offers an optimal balance between layer adhesion and part release. The use of an adhesion agent (such as hairspray) is also recommended to improve first-layer adhesion.

2.2. Material-Specific Considerations

- **Copper-Filled Filament:** Processing depends heavily on the extrusion setup. In Bowden setups, a filament preheating system (~60 °C) is required to ensure consistent flow. Direct drive systems are generally more reliable, though thermal conditioning is still beneficial. Spool orientation is critical: the spool should be positioned so the filament feeds downward, minimizing bending stresses.

- **Alumina-Filled Filament:** This material requires direct extrusion systems exclusively, as its brittleness and low flexibility make it unsuitable for Bowden configurations. Thermal conditioning (40–60 °C) is required prior to and during printing. Additionally, extruder tension must be perfectly calibrated to avoid filament fracture, and the G-code toolpath must be adapted to minimize long, high-speed travel movements that can break the material. Processing this material requires a printer capable of operating at low extrusion temperatures (<180 °C); in some cases, this may require firmware modification (e.g., root access and parameter adjustment) to override manufacturer-imposed temperature limits. In the same way, calibration must be done carefully (without filament loaded or by changing the printing calibration temperature limit) to avoid high temperatures that could degrade and carbonize filament in the nozzle.

3. Post-Processing

The process to obtain fully functional parts involves three main stages after printing:

3.1. Debinding

- **Copper:** A thermal debinding process is used. It is crucial to bury the printed parts in a proper powder (as alumina) inside a crucible to prevent deformation during heating.
- **Alumina:** Requires a two-step process starting with chemical debinding (an acetone bath followed by drying), and subsequently moving to thermal debinding.

3.2. Sintering

- **Copper:** Parts undergo a high-temperature thermal cycle. They must be kept isolated from oxygen to prevent oxidation; this is achieved by keeping them buried in alumina powder, applying a carbon layer to be burned off, and covering the crucible.
- **Alumina:** Requires high-temperature thermal sintering (1550 °C) to achieve the target relative density.

For both materials, dimensional shrinkage in the X, Y, and Z directions must be accounted for during the design phase to achieve final dimensional accuracy.

3.3. Washcoating (For Catalytic Applications)

- For ceramic alumina supports, active phases (such as noble metals) can be applied using a washcoating method. This involves successive immersions of the printed supports in a suspension, followed by intermediate drying and final calcination. To prevent the active catalytic layer from detaching, it is highly recommended to incorporate a binder, such as colloidal silica, to significantly improve the adhesion of the coating to the printed substrate.

Guide for the Design of TPMS Catalytic Supports by FFF: Part 2 Examples of Estimation Nomographs

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The Darcy-Forchheimer equation provides an estimation of the pressure drop for TPMS catalytic converters. This model depends on the permeability that can be approximated by the Scholz model, and the inertial resistance. Those parameters can be fitted by CFD analysis of unit cells. On the other hand, the mass transference can be estimated using the Sherwood number. A set of experimental measures can be used to determine the coefficients of that equation.

The following paragraphs show two examples of nomographs (Table 1 and Figure 1) derived from the previous discussion.

Cell size /mm	Critical length / mm	Permeability /mm ²
3	2,00	0,34
4	1,64	0,72
5	1,33	1,10
6	0,97	1,48
7	0,95	1,86
8	0,83	2,24
9	0,74	2,62
10	0,66	3,00
11	0,60	3,38
12	0,55	3,76
13	0,50	4,14
14	0,47	4,52
15	0,43	4,90
Gyroid Cell, wall thickness = 0.8 mm		

Figura 1: Example of table to determine the permeability

Figura 2: Nomograph example. Gyroid substrate, temperature 300 °C